

Received 01.03.2023 | Accepted 30.03.2023 | Published: 08.04.2023 (online) |
<https://doi.org/10.24386/LepHung.2023.19.1.65>
<https://zoobank.org/pub:861A0131-57D2-4C74-8C98-898C6BCA926C>
<https://zenodo.org/>
<https://epa.oszk.hu/04100/04144>

New data on the occurrence of *Opogona sacchari* (Bojer, 1853) in Hungary (Lepidoptera: Tineidae)

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Citation. Fazekas I. 2023: New data on the occurrence of *Opogona sacchari* (Bojer, 1853) in Hungary (Lepidoptera: Tineidae). – Lepidopterologica Hungarica 19(1): 65–70.

Abstract. New data and observations on *Opogona sacchari* (Bojer, 1856) from Hungary. The pest moth species is no longer only found in botanical gardens, but also in homes. Its spread is continuous in the country.

Keywords. Lepidoptera, Tineidae, *Opogona sacchari* (Bojer, 1856), the new record, Hungary.

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Introduction

In Europe, the family Tineidae comprises 278 species in 52 genera (Gaedike et al. 2018). In Hungary this group is represented by 65 species genera (Pastoralis & Buschmann 2018). According to Catania et al. (2023) the Tineidae feed on anything, from vegetative material to carcasses. The majority of the species construct cases which they carry during their larval stages and pupate within them.

According to Van Der Gaag et al. (2013) in Europe, the genus *Opogona* Zeller 1853, comprises three species, namely *Opogona omoscopia* (Meyrick, 1893) recorded from the Azores in Portugal and Sardinia in Italy; *Opogona antistacta* Meyrick, 1937, which was “bred from a larva found in London feeding under slight tubular web on the rind of banana” (Rennwald, 2022) and *Opogona sacchari* (Bojer, 1856) ranging across Africa, Asia, Europe and America.

Opogona sacchari was discovered in Hungary on 23 July 1993 by a casual florist in Budapest (Tusnádi et al. 1996). After that, the authors did not publish any further observations. In this paper, I report new observations on Hungary. I give a brief overview of the research on this species. In my opinion, *Opogona sacchari* is present in several locations in Hungary, but no observations have been reported. The study aims to draw attention to this fact.

Results

Opogona sacchari (Bojer, 1856)

Alucita sacchari Bojer, 1856 | In: Report of the Committee on the "Cane Borer": Pg. 21 pl. 5, figs 1–10.
Synonyms: *Gelechia ligniferella* Walker, 1875; *Gelechia sanctaehelenae* Walker, 1875; *Laverna plumipes* Butler, 1876; *Opogona ligniferella* (Walker, 1875); *Opogona plumipes* (Butler, 1876); *Opogona sanctaehelenae* (Walker, 1875); *Opogona subcervinella* (Bojer, 1856); *Opogona subcervinella* (Walker, 1863); *Tinea subcervinella* Walker, 1863.

This species was originally described as *Alucita sacchari* by Bojer in 1856 from Mauritius. It was later known by several names. It is currently placed in the genus *Opogona* as *O. sacchari* (Robinson & Tuck, 1997).

Diagnosis. The adult moths is nocturnal, 11–12 mm long with a wingspan of 17–25 mm. It is bright yellowish-brown. The forewings may show longitudinal darker brown banding, and in the male a dark-brown spot towards the apex. The hindwings are paler and brighter (see Fig. 3).

Bionomics. The larvae are dirty-white and transparent. They have a bright reddish-brown head, one lateral ocellus at each side, and clearly visible, brownish thoracic and abdominal

plates. They are 20–27 mm long with a diameter of 3 or 3–5 mm. The presence of older larvae can be detected by characteristic masses of bore meal and frass at the openings of boreholes. The pupae are brown, less than 10 mm long, and are formed in a cocoon, spun at the end of a mine, measuring 14–15 mm. As maturation approaches, the pupae work themselves partially out of the tissue to allow the emergence of the adult. Two bent hooks, characteristic of the species, show at the end of the abdomen on the abandoned protruding pupal skin. *Opogona sacchari* attacks several ornamental plants and can be transported on different plant parts.

According to the literature (see in References) in European countries, it has been recorded on various tropical or subtropical ornamentals, including *Alpinia*, *Begonia*, *Bougainvillea*, *Bromeliaceae*, *Cactaceae*, *Chamaedorea Dracaena*, *Strelitzia* and *Yucca*, and other palms, *Cordyline*, *Dieffenbachia*, *Euphorbia pulcherrima*, *Ficus*, *Gloxinia*, *Heliconia*, *Hippeastrum*, *Maranta*, *Philodendron*, *Sansevieria* and *Saintpaulia*, and also *Capsicum* and *Solanum melongena* (Cabi, 2022). Its larvae are difficult to detect as they feed inside the host plant tissue. This is especially so during the first larval instars which hide in cracks, bulbs, or other plant structures. (Van Der Gaag et al. 2013).

New records from Hungary. 1 female, Hungary, Nagytálya, II. Rákóczi Ferenc utca 26. in housing, 21.02.2023. leg. Szilvia Gulyás, in coll. Pannon Institute, H-Pécs. Many examples: Palm House of the Botanical Garden Budapest, Illés utca 25. 1 male Pécs, December 2022, Mecsekoldal, in the home, leg. Imre Fazekas, in coll. Pannon Institute, H-Pécs.

According to the manager of the Palm House (Botanical Garden Budapest (Fig. 1.)), it was first observed around 2019 and has been present in the stems of begonia species ever since. It was later found on banana trees. The pest has been controlled with a pesticide called Actara, but to no avail. The pest moth has been present since then and control is no longer being pursued (Peter Kiszél pers. comm; Februar 2023).

First observations in Hungary. *Opogona sacchari* was discovered in Hungary on 23 July 1993 by a casual florist in Budapest (Tusnádi et al. 1996). Infection and damage were observed on a 60 cm long and 5 cm wide *Dracaena* stem. Faeces and crab thread granules fell out of the openings. The plant was delivered to "Rozmaring Horticulture Ltd." Plant Protection Laboratory. The plant was grown in a net-covered isolator. The emerging moths were placed in Petri dishes daily and fed with sugar water. They were monitored for how long they lived, their sex and sex ratio were determined, and the number of eggs laid per female was counted. The flight of the moths took place from 3 August to 22 November. The ratio of females to males was 1:1 (32 females to 30 males). The moths lived in the Petri dishes for 1–2 days. Both sexes were present only one day at a time; the female laid 74 eggs after fertilization, but these did not hatch. After that, the authors did not publish any further observations.

At that time, Tusnádi et al. (1996) wrote: "The first occurrence of *O. sacchari* in Hungary in 1993 can be regarded as a singular, isolated case that became annihilated and has not occurred since then." The new observations in Hungary contradict the former statement. In my opinion, the species is still present in Hungary. It is no longer found only in glasshouses or plant protection laboratory, but also in rural and urban dwellings.

Overview of other important observations (schematically). According to d'Aguilar & Martinez (1982) in Europe, the species has been detected on several occasions following imports of bananas. Thus Durrant finds it in Margate (Great Britain) in 1925, Janône in the port of Genoa (Italy) in 1953 and Wolff the same year in Denmark. These were, in these cases, temporary accidental introductions. Subsequently, *O. sacchari* became acclimatized in several European countries on ornamental crops, mostly of tropical origin. The first discovery of this pest on this type of crop in Italy seems to be that of Rota in 1969 (Ciampolini, 1973 and Süß, 1974). *O. sacchari* was found in 1971 on *Strelitzia* in the Netherlands and on *Ficus* in Great Britain where, in 1976, it was collected on *Dracaena* from Guatemala. In France, this species has just been recognized in Bouches-du-Rhône at Saint-Rémy-de-Provence; the origin of its introduction is not known. The different states of this Lepidoptera have been described by Oldham (1928) and by Süß (1974).

Opogona sacchari first reached pest status in 1928 when it began to cause severe damage to bananas in the Canary Islands. It subsequently spread to other cultivated plants there (including *Strelitzia*, killing 24–40% of the plants) and continues to cause average yield losses of bananas of 5–10% in the islands, with losses of up to 30% on the island of La Palma (Pérez Padrón & Carnero Hernández 1984).

According to Lastuvka et al. (2018), in the Czech Republic found in 2000 in Frýdek-Místek and in 2004 in Ostrava on plant material (*Yucca*) probably imported from the Netherlands, in 2006 in Prague Zoo in the Indonesian Jungle Pavilion, where it was introduced in the caterpillar or egg stage with tropical fruits, in recent years several times in Brno and elsewhere.

According to Łabanowski (2017) in Poland *Opogona sacchari* (Bojer, 1856) In Poland, it was detected for the first time on the Guatemalan yucca in 1991 (Łabanowski 1999), and in 2016 on Fortune's rough wort (*Trachycarpus fortunei*), yellow-yellow areca (*Chrysalidocarpus lutescens*), lingual guzmania (*Guzmania lingulata*) and zamiokulkas. (*Zamioculcas zamiifolia*), as well as on post-insects. Due to the type of damage and high reproductive potential, it poses a great threat to the cultivation of potted plants.

There are interesting observations from far-off China. According to Ruizhen et al. (2002) the *Opogona sacchari* is a newly introduced exotic pest in China. It took 66 days to 135 days for the pest to finish a generation at 25.71 ± 2.71 deg C and $75.95\% \pm 5.02\%$ RH and might have 4 generations per year. The larval period had the longest duration, 37 to 75 days, with 7 instars recognizable through the head capsule width, and was the harmful developmental stage. The mean number of eggs laid per female was 253.05 ± 65.18 (n=20).

Japanese observations (Yoshimatsu et al 2004): This moth was also spotted in Chichi-jima, Ogasawara, in 1999. However, through the identification performed in our laboratories, a number of records on this moth have accumulated from many localities in Japan. *O. sacchari*'s presence in Japan appears to be in the warm regions of Honshu, Shikoku, Kyushu, and the Ryukyu Islands.

Summary. This species is a polyphagous pest of many host plants in the subtropical and tropical regions of Africa and has also been introduced into North Africa, North, Central and South America and Europe as well. In Europe (Belgium, Denmark, Finland, France, Greece, Netherlands, UK, Germany, and Italy) it has appeared on ornamental plants belonging to more than 20 different genera. More attention needs to be paid to its spread and damage in Hungary.

Acknowledgements. Thank you to Szilvia Gulyás (H-Nagytyálya) for sending me the specimen she collected in her home for examination. I thank Péter Kiszél (H-Botanical Garden Budapest) for the information about the observation of the species. Thanks to my colleague Zsigó György (H-Budapest) for taking the photos. Comments on the final manuscript, as well as additional linguistic tuning, were made by Colin W. Plant (UK-Bishops Stortford).

Figs 1-5. Botanical Garden Budapest (1); Street view, Nagytálya Rákóczi street (2); Adult of *Opogona sacchari* (3); larvae in faeces and feeding tunnels in *Dracaena* in Budapest (4) [photo: ©; Gy. Zsigó]; Exotic-looking yucca in the room, also known as palm lilies, are easy-to-grow, room-sized, leafy-potted trees that have enjoyed decades of popularity in Hungary (5). Larvae also attack indoor yuccas.

Fig. 6. Observed occurrences of *Opogona sacchari* in Hungary between 1993 and 2023. The distance between sites is given in km.

Fig 7. Schematic geographical distribution of *Opogona sacchari* with additions
(© <https://gd.eppo.int/taxon/OPOGSC/distribution>[accessed 18.03.2023])

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